

Project Number: 101023060

Project Acronym: MicroREvolution

Project title: MicroREvolution - a high-throughput drop-based microfluidic platform for rapid screening of highly diverse antimicrobial peptide mutant libraries generated via directed evolution

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Work package 1: Deliverables 1.1-1.3

Microfluidic device fabrication:

Throughout the project, I have designed multiple microfluidic devices and below are examples of the devices used for generating microfluidic droplets (Figure 1), picoinjecting additional fluids into the droplets (Figure 2), merging two droplets (Figure 3), the devices used in FADS experiments (Figures 4 and 5), and droplet incubation devices (Figure 6).

Figure 1. Schematic illustration of the 2 pL droplet generator. Features are 10 μm high. The oil channel is 20 μm high. The aqueous solution channel is 10 μm wide.

Figure 2. Schematic illustration of the 4 pL droplet picoinjection device. The red and blue channels correspond to the electrodes and moats, respectively. The droplet inlet channel is 20 μm wide and high. The picoinjection nozzle is 10 μm wide and 20 μm high.

Figure 3. Schematic illustration of the 9.5 pL and 2 pL droplet merging device. The red and blue channels correspond to the electrodes and moats, respectively. The droplet inlet channel is 10 μm wide and 20 μm high. The droplet generation junction is 20 μm high with 10 μm wide aqueous solution channel, 15 μm wide oil channels and 30 μm wide droplet collection channel.

Figure 4. Schematic illustration of the 25 μm diameter droplet sorter. The red and blue channels correspond to the electrodes and moats, respectively.

Figure 5. Schematic illustration of the 50 μm diameter droplet sorter. The red and blue channels correspond to the electrodes and moats, respectively.

Figure 6. Schematic illustration of microfluidic droplet collection and incubation device. Droplets can be collected from and reinjected back into the microfluidic device.

The masters of the microfluidic devices were fabricated using conventional soft-photolithography methods using SU-8-on-Si wafer masters, and polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS)-on-glass devices. Briefly, the SU-8 3000 series photoresist (A-Gas Electronic Materials Limited) was poured on a polished silicon wafer (MicroChemicals GmbH) and spun down for 45 seconds at appropriate RPM (See Figure 7) using a spin coater. Subsequently, the SU-8 coated wafer was soft-baked on a level hot plate at 95 °C for an appropriate time (See Table 1). After the soft bake step, the SU-8 coated wafer was cooled down to room temperature and then the acetate sheet mask with the design of the device was placed on top of it. Mask-SU-8 coated wafer sandwich was exposed to the UV light for 40 seconds. Directly after the exposure, the mask was removed and the SU-8 coated wafer was post-exposure baked (PEB) on a level hot plate at 95 °C for 5 min. After PEB, the developing step took place by submerging the SU-8 coated wafer into propylene glycol monomethyl ether acetate (PGMEA; Sigma-Aldrich) solution and incubating it for 2-8 min with periodical agitation. Finally, the wafer was rinsed with isopropyl alcohol and dried under airflow. The master wafer for fabricating microfluidic devices was obtained.

Figure 7. SU-8 3000 series thickness vs. spin speed.

Thickness, μm	Soft bake time, min at 95 °C
4-10	2-3
8-15	5-10
20-50	10-15
30-90	10-30
40-100	15-45

Table 1. Soft bake times

The microfluidic devices were fabricated by casting PDMS (Sylgard 184 kit; Dow Corning) on a master wafer, curing it at 65 °C for 60 min, peeling it off, punching the holes for inlets and outlets, and bonding it to a 1 mm thick glass slide (EpreDia) after oxygen plasma activation in plasma oven (Diener Femto, 40% power for 30 seconds). Subsequently, hydrophobic treatment of the channels of the microfluidic device was performed. The channels were filled with 1 % v/v trichloro(1H,1H,2H,2H-perfluorooctyl)silane (Sigma-Aldrich) in HFE-7500 fluorinated oil (3M™ Novec™ Engineered fluid) solution and incubated for 30 min. After the incubation, channels were washed with HFE-7500 fluorinated oil and dried under airflow.

Droplet collection and incubation device is made by punching 1 mm holes at the top and side of the Eppendorf tube using a 1 mm biopsy puncher, inserting and glueing 1 mm outer diameter and 0.38 mm inner diameter polyethylene (PE) tubing using UV curable glue (LOCTITE AA 350), and glueing the tube to a 1 mm thick glass slide using the same glue.

Standard Operating procedures

Microfluidic droplet generation:

2 pL microfluidic droplets can be generated using a microfluidic device shown in Figure 1 (Figure 8). 1 mL disposable syringes (BD Luer-Lok) are filled with: #1 HFE-7500 oil supplemented with 2% fluorosurfactant (RAN Biotechnologies); #2 Aqueous solution containing plasmid DNA; and #3 GenomiPhi V2 DNA amplification mix. The syringes are connected to the microfluidic device via Masterflex PTFE microbore tubing (0.76 mm outer diameter and 0.3 mm inner diameter). The flow rates of the solutions are controlled using Cetoni Nemesys syringe pumps. To make 2 pL droplets, the flow rates have to be $\sim 100 \mu\text{L/h}$ for oil and $\sim 25 \mu\text{L/h}$ for each aqueous solution. The droplet size, and hence the volume, can be controlled by changing the ratio between the oil and aqueous solutions flow rates.

Figure 8. Representative images of microfluidic droplet generation. Due to laminar flow, the aqueous solutions do not mix until they are encapsulated into the droplet, where they rapidly mix before leaving the device.

Picoinjection:

Picoinjection is a microfluidic technique that enables one to introduce additional components into pre-formed droplets. In the context of this project, this was a crucial technique that enabled the decoupling of the in-droplet single plasmid DNA amplification reaction and the cell-free protein synthesis, which are not compatible with each other. Picoinjection can be performed using the microfluidic device shown in Figure 2 (Figure 9). 1 mL disposable syringes (BD Luer-Lok) are filled with: #1 HFE-7500 oil supplemented with 2% fluorosurfactant (RAN Biotechnologies); #2 Aqueous solution containing cell-free protein synthesis mix (NEBExpress, NEB); #3 and #4 syringes filled with 5 M NaCl (electrodes). The syringes are connected to the microfluidic device via a 27 gauge needle and Masterflex PTFE microbore tubing (0.76 mm outer diameter and 0.3 mm inner diameter). The droplet incubation device (Figure 6) is connected to the droplet inlet via PTFE microbore tubing. The picoinjection is performed by flowing the pre-formed droplets past the channel with the reagent to be introduced. A thin layer of surfactant, present on the droplets, prevents them from merging with each other or the liquid from being injected. Therefore, this layer has to be destabilised by applying an electric field. The function generator (33250A, Agilent) generates a sine wave of 0-10 V amplitude and 10 kHz frequency and the high-voltage amplifier (HVA200, Thorlabs) amplifies this signal to 50-200 V. This signal is then applied to the liquid electrodes via alligator clips connected to an exposed section of the syringe needle attached to syringes pre-filled with 5 M NaCl to generate an electric field enabling the injection. The injected liquid volume can be adjusted by altering the flow of injected fluid, altering the flow of droplets and oil (changes the frequency at which droplets arrive at the injection junction) or both. Typical flow rates are 90 $\mu\text{L}/\text{h}$ for spacing oil, 60 $\mu\text{L}/\text{h}$ for reagents to be injected, and 30 $\mu\text{L}/\text{h}$ for reinjected droplets.

Figure 9. Representative brightfield images of picoinjection. The droplets are re-injected into the device via the droplet inlet and then spaced out using spacing oil. The water/oil interfaces of droplets passing the picoinjection junction are destabilised by a localised electric field enabling the additional reagents (green) to enter the droplet. Once away from the electric field, the drops regain their stability, and do not merge, even when in contact.

Droplet merging:

Merging of surfactant-stabilised microfluidic droplets can be achieved by using the microfluidic device shown in Figure 3. 1 mL disposable syringes (BD Luer-Lok) are filled with: #1 and #2 HFE-7500 oil supplemented with 2% fluorosurfactant (RAN Biotechnologies); #3 Aqueous solution containing cell-free protein synthesis mix (NEBExpress, NEB) or bacterial cells; #4 and #5 syringes filled with 5 M NaCl (electrodes). The syringes are connected to the microfluidic device via a 27 gauge needle and Masterflex PTFE microbore tubing (0.76 mm outer diameter and 0.3 mm inner diameter). The droplet incubation device (Figure 6) is connected to the droplet inlet via PTFE microbore tubing. First, two different populations of droplets are paired (Figure 10). The pairing works well only if the size of the droplets being paired is different. The smaller droplet can easily catch up with the bigger one due to lower drag along the sidewalls of the channel. Later, paired droplets flow through an area that is exposed to a localised electric field, which destabilises the water/oil interfaces of droplets in close proximity and facilitates their merging (Figure 11). Once away from the electric field, the drops regain their stability, and do not merge, even when in contact. The electric field is generated by the function generator (TG 2000, Aim-TTi) that generates a sine wave of 0-10 V amplitude and 20 kHz frequency and the high-voltage amplifier (Trek 2210, Advanced Energy) that amplifies this signal to 300-1000 V. The signal is applied to the liquid electrodes via alligator clips connected to an exposed section of the syringe needle attached to syringes pre-filled with 5 M NaCl solution.

Figure 10. Representative brightfield images of droplet pairing. The flows were: 200 $\mu\text{L}/\text{h}$ for both spacing oil and droplet-generating oil, 60 $\mu\text{L}/\text{h}$ for aqueous solution, and 50 $\mu\text{L}/\text{h}$ for reinjected droplets.

Figure 11. Representative brightfield images of droplet merging process. Upon exposure to electric field, the water/oil interfaces of paired droplets in close proximity are destabilised enabling droplet merging.

Fluorescence activated droplet sorting:

For this project, I have engineered and built a custom fluorescence-activated droplet sorting (FADS) platform that enables one to sort microfluidic droplets based on their fluorescence intensity (Figure 12) using the microfluidic devices shown in Figures 4 and 5. The platform comprises of a laser light source (C-FLEX laser beam combiner housing 445, 488, 561 and 630 nm lasers, Cobolt) which is fibre-coupled to collimating beam expander (60FC-T-4-M40L-24, Schaefer & Kirchhoff GmbH); the $\varnothing 25$ mm steering mirrors that enable the precise position of the beam; the cylindrical lens (ACY254-050-A, Thorlabs) that shapes laser beam into a line; $\varnothing 12.5$ mm tube lens (LA1560-A-ML, Thorlabs) that collimates line source; excitation dichroic mirror that reflects the light into the objective and transmits the emitted light through (DI01-R405/488/561/635-25X36, Laser2000); $\varnothing 25$ mm turning mirror that reflect the light into and back from the back of the objective; the 20X objective (MRH00201, Nikon); custom-built sample stage that enables to move the sample in XYZ directions; IR light source for brightfield imaging (M810L3-C1, Thorlabs); emission dichroic mirror (FF757-DI01-25X36, Laser2000) that reflect emitted light into the photomultiplier tube (PMT, detector) and enables transmission of brightfield illumination to pass to the high-speed camera (Miro C210, Phantom); the mount with interchangeable filter lenses (CFH2R, Thorlabs); PMT that enables detection of emitted light signal (PMM02, Thorlabs); data acquisition card (DAQ; Arduino Due, Arduino) that allows to compare the signal recorded by the PMT with the set threshold and make a decision whether the droplet should be sorted; pulse generator (TGP110, Aim-TTi) that generates a 10 V pulse of desired length and delay upon being triggered by the DAQ; the pulse generator-controlled function generator (TG 2000, Aim-TTi) working in external gated mode, generating a 10-kHz square wave signal at an adjustable amplitude (0-10 V) which was then amplified $100\times$ using a high-voltage amplifier (TREK 2210, Advanced Energy) to actuate the sorter. The sorting signal was applied to the liquid electrodes via alligator clips connected to an exposed section of the syringe needle attached to syringes pre-filled with 5 M NaCl solution. for droplets.

Droplet sorting procedure: First, the focus of the laser beam is checked. The laser beam should appear as a sharp 5-10 μm wide and ~ 200 μm long line (Figure 13a). If the line focus is distorted, the focus can be adjusted by changing the relative distance between beam beam-shaping lens and the tube lens. If the laser beam is not perpendicular to the droplet channel, the orientation of the beam can be changed by turning the beam-shaping lens. The electrode (red) and moat (blue) channels are pre-filled with 5 M NaCl solution. The high-voltage cables are connected to the liquid electrodes via alligator clips connected to an exposed section of the syringe needle attached to the syringes. Droplets stored in the droplet storage device (Figure 6) were reinjected into the droplet sorting device (Figures 4 or 5) using syringe pumps (Nemesys, Cetoni). Typical flows were: 400 $\mu\text{L}/\text{h}$ for spacing oil and 10-20 $\mu\text{L}/\text{h}$ for droplets. When droplets pass the laser beam, the emitted fluorescence intensity is recorded by PMT and converted into a voltage signal between 0 and 10 V. The output voltage of PMT is continuously measured by DAQ, which compares the measured voltage with the set threshold. The C++-based Arduino script used for signal processing and decision-making is provided below. An example of a microfluidic droplet being sorted is shown in Figure 13b.

Figure 12. Schematic illustration of FADS platform engineered and built for this project.

Figure 13. Microfluidic droplet sorting. Laser beam focusing and positioning (a). Time-lapse images of droplet sorting experiment (b). The fluorescence intensity of the droplets is continuously measured, in the provided example, the droplet with a fluorescent particle inside is pulled to the electrode (red) and is moved to the collection channel. The empty droplets naturally move to the low-resistance waste channel.

Sorting script:

```
//Sorting Parameters
const float sortThresh = 8; // sorting threshold in volts
const float dropletThresh = 2; // droplet threshold in volts
const float maxVoltage = 10; // max measured voltage in volts
const int minResidence = 2; // minimal droplet residence time in microseconds
const int maxResidence=500; // maximal droplet residence time in microseconds
const int outputSource = 13; //connect this pin to pulse generator
const int outputSource2 = 12; //connect this pin to oscilloscope
const int outputSource3 = 11; //connect this pin to camera trigger
const int inputSource = A0; //connect to PMT

//Other Global Variables
float fluorRead;
long dropletWidth;
long dropletTimerEnd;
long dropletTimerStart;

//fluorescence read
float reading(){
fluorRead = analogRead(inputSource); // read the signal from PMT
fluorRead = fluorRead/4096*10; //change 4096 depending on analogReadResolution
return fluorRead;
}

void setup() {
Serial.begin(9600);
pinMode(outputSource, OUTPUT);
pinMode(outputSource2, OUTPUT);
pinMode(outputSource3, OUTPUT);
analogReadResolution(12); // set analog read resolution in bits
REG_ADC_MR = (REG_ADC_MR & 0xFFF0FFFF) || 0x00020000; // increase analog read
speed by 10 fold
}

// Pulses according to parameters
void pulse(){
delayMicroseconds(50);
digitalWrite(outputSource, HIGH);
digitalWrite(outputSource2, HIGH);
digitalWrite(outputSource3, HIGH);
delayMicroseconds(50);
digitalWrite(outputSource, LOW);
digitalWrite(outputSource2, LOW);
digitalWrite(outputSource3, LOW);
}

// Sorting algorithm
void sort (){
fluorRead = reading();
```

```
if (fluorRead > dropletThresh){
if (fluorRead > sortThresh){
while (fluorRead > dropletThresh && fluorRead < maxVoltage){ //change maxVoltage if you
want to collect droplets with lower fluorescence intensity than the majority of the population
fluorRead = reading();
}
dropletTimerEnd = micros();
dropletWidth = dropletTimerEnd-dropletTimerStart;
if (dropletWidth > minResidence && dropletWidth < maxResidence){
pulse();
}
}
}
else
dropletTimerStart = micros();
}
// Main loop
void loop(){
sort();
}
```

The signal from PMT and the sorting trigger signal from DAQ are also recorded using a USB-connected oscilloscope (PicoScope 4424, pico Technology) which enables fast data collection. Collected data is saved as a .CSV file and plotted using a custom Python script (provided below). An example data set is provided (Figure 14). The residence time, and hence the size, of the droplets is also measured enabling to have a droplet size threshold. Thus, droplets are sorted not only by the fluorescence intensity but also based on their size.

Figure 14. Example data set of microfluidic droplet sorting experiment. Analysis of droplets with *E. coli* cells incubated in the absence (a) and presence (b) of kanamycin. Using Poisson distribution, the average encapsulation rate was chosen to be 0.5 cells per droplet, which should result in 30% of droplets containing a single cell and the rest should be empty. In the example data set a, the data from 42426 droplets was collected, and 14141 droplets had a signal above the set threshold, which is $\sim 33\%$ of the population. In the data set b, the data from 28463 droplets was collected, and only 55 had a signal above the threshold. So, if we assume that the signal intensity in data set b comes only from empty droplets and droplets that had cells which could not multiply due to the presence of antibiotics, we see that in data set a 67% of droplets were empty and 33% had cells that multiplied (the signal intensity is proportional to the amount of the C12-resazurin reduced to red-fluorescent C12-resorufin in metabolically active cells).

Data plotting script:

```
import numpy as np
import scipy.signal
import pandas as pd
import peakutils.baseline
from matplotlib import pyplot as plt
import os
import glob
import matplotlib.gridspec as gridspec
import matplotlib as mpl
from matplotlib import ticker
formatter = ticker.ScalarFormatter(useMathText=True)
formatter.set_scientific(True)
formatter.set_powerlimits((-1,1))
mpl.rcParams['figure.dpi']=300
mpl.rcParams['savefig.dpi']=600

#use glob to get all the csv files in the folder
path = r'insert path to the folder with csv data files'
csv_files = glob.glob(os.path.join(path, "*.csv"))

x = [ ]
y = [ ]
z = [ ]

for f in csv_files:
df = pd.read_csv(f, skiprows=3, header=None)
x.extend(df[0])
y.extend(df[1])
z.extend(df[2])

resolution = (x[2]-x[1])1000 #If the original time scale is in seconds you need to use * 1000
time_ms = np.arange(0,np.shape(x)[0]*resolution,resolution)
total_time_s = time_ms/1000
total_time = time_ms
Time = np.array(time_ms)
Voltage = np.array(y)
Voltage = np.nan_to_num(Voltage, nan = 0)
Trigger = np.array(z)
baseline = peakutils.baseline(Voltage)
average_baseline = np.mean(baseline)
std_baseline = np.std(baseline)
print("Baseline at:", np.round(average_baseline, decimals = 3))
droplet_threshold = 1 #adjust to the desired threshold
hits_threshold = 3 #adjust to the desired threshold
distance_between_peaks = 200 #number of samples between neighbouring peaks
relative_height = 0.5 #the relative height at which peak width is measured, e.g. 0.5 is at half
the prominence height
sample_rate = 5 #sample rate of detector
bins = 100 #number of histogram bins
```

```

residence_time_low = 100 #minimum residence time for gating in microseconds
residence_time_high = 200 #maximum residence time for gating in microseconds
Trigger = Trigger/3.3*hits_threshold

#peak detection
maxima = scipy.signal.find_peaks(Voltage,distance=distance_between_peaks,
height=droplet_threshold)#find all dropelts
maxima_sort = scipy.signal.find_peaks(Voltage,distance=distance_between_peaks,
height=(hits_threshold,10.2)) #find all droplets above threshold
points, _ = maxima
points_sort,_ = maxima_sort
max_pos = Time[maxima[0]]
max_height = Voltage[maxima[0]]
max_pos_sort = Time[maxima_sort[0]]
max_height_sort = Voltage[maxima_sort[0]]

#peak detection with gating
peak_widths = scipy.signal.peak_widths(Voltage,points, rel_height=relative_height)
peak_widths1 = scipy.signal.peak_widths(Voltage,points_sort, rel_height=relative_height)
widths = peak_widths[0]
widths1 = peak_widths1[0]
residence_time = widths*sample_rate
residence_time1 = widths1*sample_rate
residence_time_gated = residence_time[np.where((residence_time >= residence_time_low) &
(residence_time <= residence_time_high))]
residence_time_gated1 = residence_time1[np.where((residence_time1 >= residence_time_low)
& (residence_time1 <= residence_time_high))]
points1 = points[np.where((residence_time >= residence_time_low) & (residence_time <=
residence_time_high))]
points_sort1 = points_sort[np.where((residence_time1 >= residence_time_low) &
(residence_time1 <= residence_time_high))]
gated_voltage = Voltage[points1]
# gated_voltage1 = Voltage[points_sort1]

#graph plotting gs = gridspec.GridSpec(2,2, wspace = 0.5, hspace = 0.55, top = 0.94)

#voltage against time
fig = plt.figure(figsize = (6,4))
ax1 = fig.add_subplot(gs[1,:])
ax1.plot(Time,Voltage, linewidth = 1, c = 'k')
ax1.plot(Time,Trigger, linewidth = 1, color = 'deeppink', linestyle = '-')
ax1.scatter(max_pos,max_height,color='tab:blue',s=50,marker='x')
ax1.scatter(max_pos_sort,max_height_sort,color='red',s=50,marker='x')
ax1.plot((Time[0],Time[-1]),(hits_threshold,hits_threshold), linewidth = 1, linestyle = '-', c =
'tab:orange', zorder = -1)
ax1.set_axisbelow(True)
ax1.set_xlim(5044,5049)
ax1.set_ylim(0,5.2)
# plot line where peak width was measured
# ax1.hlines(y=peak_widths[1], xmin=peak_widths[2]/200, xmax = peak_widths[3]/200, color
= "red")

```

```

plt.xlabel("Time [ms]")
plt.ylabel("PMT Signal [V]")
plt.legend(['Signal', 'Trigger', 'Drops', 'Positive Drops', 'Threshold' ], ncol = 5, fontsize = 8,
bbox_to_anchor=(0.5, 1.2),loc='upper center', fancybox = False, frameon = False)
ax1.grid()

#voltage against residence time
ax2 = fig.add_subplot(gs[0,1])
colors = np.where(Voltage[points1]< hits_threshold,'tab:blue','tab:red')
ax2.scatter(residence_time_gated,gated_voltage, alpha=0.2, s = 10, c = colors)
ax = plt.gca()
x_lim = ax.get_xlim()
ax2.plot(x_lim,(hits_threshold,hits_threshold), linewidth = 1, linestyle = '-', color = 'tab:orange',
zorder = -1)
ax2.set_xlabel("Residence time [3BCs]")
ax2.set_ylabel("Voltage [V]")
ax2.set_ylim(0,10.2)

#histogram of droplet detection signals [V]
ax3 = fig.add_subplot(gs[0,0])
ax3.hist(gated_voltage,bins=bins)
ax = plt.gca()
y_lim = ax.get_ylim()
ax3.plot((hits_threshold,hits_threshold),y_lim, linewidth = 1, linestyle = '-', color = 'tab:orange')
ax3.set_xlabel("PMT signal [V]")
ax3.set_ylabel("Relative frequency")
#ax3.set_yscale('log')
ax3.yaxis.set_major_formatter(formatter)
ax3.set_xlim(0,10.2)

# statistics
frequency = points1.size/max(total_time_s)
print(np.around(frequency,decimals = 1),"droplets per second")
print(points1.size, "droplets detected")
print(points_sort1.size,"droplets detected above threshold")
print(np.around(np.mean(residence_time_gated),2), "avg residence time [3BCs]")
V_values_above_threshold = Voltage[points_sort1[:99]]
print("Standard deviation of droplet voltages detected above
threshold:",np.round(np.std(V_values_above_threshold), decimals = 3), "volts")
stats = np.around(frequency,decimals = 1), points1.size, points_sort1.size,
np.around(np.mean(residence_time_gated), decimals = 2),
np.round(np.std(V_values_above_threshold), decimals = 3)
stats = np.array(stats)
stats = np.transpose(stats)
text = ['droplets per second:', 'droplets detected:', 'droplets above threshold:', 'avg residence
time [us]:','Std of droplet voltages detected above threshold:']
text= np.array(text)
print_stats = text, stats
print_stats = np.transpose(print_stats)
np.savetxt(path+'stats.txt', print_stats, fmt = '%s')
plt.savefig(path+'results.png')

```

```
plt.tight_layout()  
plt.show()
```
